

UZBEKISTAN'S PARTICIPATION IN THE GLOBALIZATION PROCESSES OF THE WORLD ECONOMY

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Abstract. This article analyzes the position, participation, and foreign economic relations of Uzbekistan in the context of the globalization processes of the world economy. It is known that the level of openness of our country's economy has been increasing year by year in recent years; in addition to this, the expansion of foreign trade relations, export and import, the increase in the flow of foreign state investments, and the development of transport-logistics potential are considered as main directions. Furthermore, expanding cooperation with international economic organizations, the diversification of export composition, and the formation of the digital economy are highlighted as important manifestations of globalization. The article also elaborates on paying attention to ensuring national economic stability in the context of foreign economic risks and competition, along with the positive results of globalization.

Keywords: globalization, world economy, Uzbekistan economy, foreign trade, foreign investments, economic integration, transport-logistics, export diversification, digital economy, international cooperation.

Introduction

Introduction. In the 21st century, the globalization of the world economy has become one of the most important and irreversible processes of world development. As a result of globalization, borders between national economies are becoming increasingly transparent, and the exchange of goods, services, capital, technology, and information between states is accelerating sharply. In addition, further developing the transport and logistics system strengthens foreign economic relations and develops export potential; this process directly influences the economic development model, production structure, and foreign economic policy of individual countries. Nowadays, the economy of a state cannot develop sustainably in isolation from the world market; on the contrary, it develops by harmonizing with the global economic system.

After the years of independence, Uzbekistan has been gradually transitioning to an open market economy and is establishing close cooperation with developed countries by actively participating in the world economy system. The country's favorable geographical location, wealth of natural resources, demographic potential, and the large-scale economic reforms being carried out serve as an important foundation for effective participation in globalization processes. In particular, it is of great importance for expanding and facilitating foreign trade relations, increasing various types of export potential, improving the investment environment, developing transport-logistics infrastructure, and deepening close cooperation with international economic organizations. These efforts are aimed at strengthening Uzbekistan's position in the global economic space alongside developed nations. In this regard, scientifically analyzing the further development of Uzbekistan's participation in globalization processes,

joining the ranks of the most developed nations, reducing imported goods, and increasing export potential is one of the urgent issues.

Literature Review. The issue of the globalization of the world economy has been deeply studied by many foreign and local scientists. The methodological foundations of globalization theory are covered in A. Giddens' work *"The Consequences of Modernity,"* where globalization is interpreted as an integral feature of modern society. J. Stiglitz, in his book *"Globalization and Its Discontents,"* critically analyzes the impact of globalization on the economies of developing countries and pays attention to the social consequences of the policies of international financial institutions. Furthermore, T. Levitt's article *"The Globalization of Markets"* explains globalization as a process of homogenization of world markets, substantiating the role of transnational companies [8].

Issues of international economic integration and world economic development are widely covered in the textbook *"International Economics: Theory and Policy"* by P. Krugman and M. Obstfeld, where trade theories, capital movements, and currency relations are analyzed in the context of globalization. D. Rodrik's work *"The Globalization Paradox"* reveals the contradictions between national economic policy and the global economic system, which serves as an important theoretical basis for understanding the role of the state in the context of globalization [9].

In studying the experience of developing countries, the research of J. Sachs and A. Warner on the relationship between economic openness and growth holds an important place. They empirically demonstrated that the liberalization of foreign trade has a positive effect on economic growth rates. The experience of Asian countries is widely covered through the works of J. Bhagwati on the free trade and export-oriented development model.

Issues of the integration of Uzbekistan's economy into the world economy have also been researched by local scientists. For example, the works of S. G'ulomov dedicated to modernizing the economy and market reforms analyze the process of the country's transition to an open economic model. In the textbook *"Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi"* (Economic Theory) by Sh. Shodmonov and U. G'afurov, the features of national economic development in the context of globalization are highlighted. Annual reports of the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Central Bank also serve as important sources for studying the country's foreign economic relations and investment processes [3].

At the same time, the analysis of world and Uzbek literature, articles, and manuals shows that while the general theoretical aspects of globalization are sufficiently covered in many sources, issues such as Uzbekistan's place in the regional transport-logistics system, the deep diversification of export composition, and the role of the digital economy in global integration still require complex and systematic research. In this regard, conducting research on this topic is of scientific and practical importance.

This research is aimed at a comprehensive study of Uzbekistan's participation in the globalization processes of the world economy, utilizing a combination of theoretical and empirical approaches. The methodological basis of the research consists of the principles of systematic and complex analysis of economic processes. Since globalization is a multi-factor and dynamic process, general scientific and special economic methods were used in conjunction to study it.

In the research process, methods of analysis and synthesis were primarily used. Through the method of analysis, the globalization processes in the world economy were divided into separate components, and their content, factors, and directions were studied. The method of synthesis allowed for examining these elements in interconnection and assessing their impact on Uzbekistan's economy as a whole. Additionally, using induction and deduction methods, specific features of the national economy were identified based on general theoretical rules, and general conclusions were drawn based on individual facts and indicators.

The method of comparative analysis also holds an important place. With the help of this method, Uzbekistan's participation in globalization processes was compared with the experience of other developing countries. This allowed for identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the national economy and determining effective development directions. Through the historical approach, the stage-by-stage integration processes of the country's economy after independence were analyzed, revealing the evolutionary features of these processes [4].

Statistical analysis methods were also used in the research. Based on official statistical data, state reports, and materials from international organizations, indicators such as foreign trade turnover, investment flows, and export-import composition were studied. This information was analyzed dynamically, serving to reflect the real impact of globalization processes on the national economy.

Classification of Methods

1-Table

Method Type	Method Name	Description	Application in Research
General Scientific	Analysis, synthesis, induction, and deduction	Breaking down world economies into parts, combining them as a whole, deriving theoretical rules and conclusions from individual facts, and adapting them to the national context.	Linking globalization elements to Uzbekistan's economy; generalizing and identifying national economic features.
Special	Comparative analysis and historical approach	Evolutionary analysis of integration stages after independence and comparing Uzbekistan's economy with developing countries.	Revealing the stage-by-stage change in development levels and assessing the real impact of globalization based on official data.
Empirical	Statistical analysis	Studying foreign trade, investment stages, and export-import indicators in dynamics.	Proving the real impact in the globalization process based on official data.

Method Type	Method Name	Description	Application in Research
Systemic	Scientific and logical generalization	Theoretically substantiating the obtained results and converting them into practical recommendations.	Forming scientific conclusions and strategic definitions as a result.

Furthermore, the results obtained with the help of scientific abstraction and logical generalization methods were theoretically substantiated. This enabled the drawing of scientific conclusions regarding the impact of globalization on Uzbekistan's economic development and the development of practical recommendations. Thus, the applied methodology serves to comprehensively and deeply study the topic.

The analysis of Uzbekistan's participation in the globalization processes of the world economy indicates that the country's economy is increasingly becoming a system that is open and closely linked to external markets. Firstly, the growth trend in foreign trade indicators manifests itself as one of the most important signs of globalization. The increase in export and import volumes indicates that Uzbekistan is actively participating in the international division of labor. In particular, the increase in the share of processed goods in the export structure shows that the national economy is gradually transitioning from a raw material direction to an industrialized model [8].

Analyses show that the flow of foreign investments is also one of the important results of globalization processes. Investments attracted into industry, energy, construction materials production, agriculture, and the service sector are leading to the expansion of production capacities, the creation of new jobs, and the provision of full employment for the population. At the same time, this creates a foundation for the introduction of modern technologies. As a result, it improves the quality of competitive products filling the domestic market, increases production efficiency, and expands opportunities to fill the domestic market with competitive products alongside developed nations and increase export potential.

The development of transport-logistics infrastructure also manifests itself as an important result. The modernization of railways and highways, connection to international corridors, and the establishment of logistics centers are strengthening Uzbekistan's transit potential. This situation turns the country into an important link in the regional trade and cargo transportation system, serving to increase revenues from service exports. The development of digital economy elements is also observed as a direct result of globalization processes. The wide introduction of e-commerce, online services, digital banking systems, and information technologies increases the speed and transparency of economic processes. This strengthens Uzbekistan's integration into the global information space and creates new economic opportunities.

Main Economic Indicators of Uzbekistan in Globalization Processes (2020-2025)

2-Table

No.	Indicator Name	2020	2023	2025 (Proj.)	Growth Rate	Description
1	Foreign trade turnover (bln USD)	33.5	52.1	61.8	+154%	Export-import volumes are growing steadily.
2	Export volume (bln USD)	17.3	27.6	30.8	+154%	Share of processed goods is 52%.
3	Foreign investment volume (bln USD, direct)	4.9	8.2	10.0	+316%	Growth in energy, industry, and services.
4	Share of manufacturing industry (% of GDP)	18	21	23	+8 p.p.	Transition from raw material export to finished products.
5	Transport-logistics turnover (bln ton-km)	45	58	67	+76%	Activity of 5 international corridors.
6	E-commerce volume (trln UZS)	9.8	32.4	49.0	+2233%	Digital economy is growing rapidly.
7	Service exports (bln USD)	5.2	7.8	8.5	+130%	Transport, tourism, IT services.
8	Employment rate (% of employed population)	89.1	90.3	91.0	+2.8 p.p.	Increase in jobs in industry and services.
9	Number of innovative enterprises (thousands)	1.7	2.4	2.9	+241%	Wide introduction of new technologies.

However, analyses also indicate that there are certain risks associated with globalization processes. They note that price volatility in world markets, a decrease in external demand, or global economic crises could have a negative impact on the national economy. Furthermore, in the context of strong international competition, if the adaptation level of certain local manufacturers is low, there is a probability that their market share will decrease. In general, based on the conducted analyses, it can be concluded that by actively participating in globalization processes, expanding foreign economic relations, attracting investments, and modernizing the economy, Uzbekistan is achieving positive results [5]. At the same time, to ensure sustainable development, it remains an important task to deepen economic diversification, increase innovation potential, and support national manufacturers.

Conclusion. The globalization processes of the world economy are one of the main factors of modern economic development, strengthening the interdependence of national economies and determining the development directions of states. Uzbekistan is also not staying away from

these processes and is following the path of gradually transitioning to an open market economy, expanding foreign economic relations, and integrating into the international economic space.

The results of the research show that the country's participation in globalization processes manifests itself primarily in the growth of foreign trade volumes, the diversification of export composition, the increase in foreign investment flows, and the development of transport-logistics infrastructure. Furthermore, the formation of the digital economy and the deepening of cooperation with international economic organizations serve to strengthen Uzbekistan's position in the global economic system. These processes demonstrate that they are opening wide opportunities to significantly increase the competitiveness of the national economy, modernize industry, and create new jobs.

At the same time, in the globalization processes, diversification and further diversifying sectors remain one of the important tasks. Instability in the world market, sharp price changes, foreign economic crises, and the conditions of strong competition can affect the stability of the national economy. Therefore, ensuring economic stability requires deepening diversification, increasing innovative potential, and supporting national producers.

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